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**Every man is consumer, and ought to be a producer.
He is by constitution expensive, and needs to be rich.**

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WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN SERVICE SECTOR

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Work-life balance is a concept which includes proper prioritizing between "work" and "lifestyle". Work life Balance of women employees has become an important subject because the time has changed from men earning the family living to where both men and women equally share the responsibility of earning for the betterment of their family life. Work-Life Balance does not mean an equal balance between work and family life but it means the capacity to schedule the hours of professional and personal life so as to lead a healthy and peaceful life. Work life balance is not a new concept and it also put more weightage on the values, attitudes and beliefs of women regarding their age to work in organizing and balancing their work and personal life. When a woman achieves a successful work-life balance, she has job satisfaction and becomes highly committed and productive and succeeds in her career. Studies have shown that the majority of women are working 40-45 hrs/week out of which almost 53% of them struggle to achieve work-life-balance. The reason behind this struggle is that they are being challenged by the demands of their organization versus the commitments of their home. They need to manage the daily requirements of their family as one side and the multiple schedules, meetings, business requirements and other routine responsibilities at work. Women at work need to be take care by their employers.

The factors influencing the experience of work-life balance were identified while reviewing the international literature and they are as follows. (i) The multiple roles performed by women (ii) Organization culture and work dynamics (iii) Personal resources and social support (iv) Career orientation and career (v) Coping and coping strategies.

To achieve a positive work-Life Balance, women should be pro-active and plan her professional and personal schedules well in advance so that both are equally balanced and the end result is satisfaction.

Introduction

Work – life Balance of women employees has become an important subject since the time has changed from men was the breadwinner, to today's world where both men and women equally sharing the responsibility of family life. Though it is a very broad subject which speaks about both career development on one side and the family care on the other side, it is very necessary to know how the women balance the professional demands and domestic compulsions.

Professional life means the aim to grow and earn respect in the organization and society at large and Personal life means taking care of family, children, parents, health and spending the leisure time effectively.

With the development in educational, economical and social standards, things have improved to a great extent and the role of women in balancing their lifestyle is less taxing. But not all women have been able to achieve this balance, as each one of them has different challenges to balance. Therefore

only periodical research will bring to light the inadequacies of the initiatives to achieve a healthy work life balance.

Work/life balance is a concept that significantly affects the health and happiness of one's life. The concept rests on your agenda for demarcating the amount of time you spend with work and the amount of time you spend in leisurely pursuits, where leisure is everything outside the scope of your work. Work/life balance is an area of research dating back to the 1960s. In fact, it began as a topic of study in management as an attempt to formulate working conditions that maximized productivity for industrial companies. It has often been a theme of political and social discussion, and it is important, to realize that different societies have different perceptions about what a suitable work/life balance is.

Indian families are undergoing rapid changes due to the increased pace of urbanization and modernization. Indian women belonging to all classes have entered into paid occupations. At the present time, Indian women's exposure to educational opportunities is substantially higher than it was some decades ago, especially in the urban setting. This has opened new vistas, increased awareness and raised aspirations of personal growth. This, along with economic pressure, has been instrumental in influencing women's decision to enter the work force. Most studies of employed women in India have reported economic need as being the primary reason given for working.

Work-life balance

An increasing number of articles have promoted the importance of work-life balance. This highlights the current concern

within society and organizations about the impact of multiple roles on the health and well-being of women employees and its implications regarding work and family performance, and women's role in society. The following variables influencing the experience of work-life balance were identified while reviewing the international literature.

Importance of Work Life Balance for Women Employees

Studies have shown that the majority of women are working 40 - 45 hrs/week out of which almost 53% of them struggle to achieve work life balance. The reason behind this struggle is that they are being challenged by the demands of their organization versus the commitments of their home. They need to manage the daily requirements of their family as one side and the multiple schedules, meetings, business requirements and other routine responsibilities at work. Women at work need to be take care by their employers. Employer's schemes that would not only attract and retain the employees for a longer period but also make them highly productive.

Organizations have many such facilities like Transport, Canteen, Day care centres, Postal/saving schemes, Flexi working hours, part time working, provide the information about work life balance policies and special leave arrangement such as Annual leave & public holiday leave, Career Break leave for elective representative, Health care centres, rewards & recognition, career growth, Insurance plans, Job rotation, Incentives, Performance related pays, Rest rooms and other government schemes like maternity, marriage, sick leave benefit, &

medical benefits, Staff counselling, Organizational psychology unit, Workplace Health Promotion, Social clubs, Preretirement club, Women's network, Breast feeding support groups etc. These schemes help the women employees to work peacefully without any family, children tension so that they are able to give their best at work. Moreover, organizations have women empowerment schemes like Forums, Committees, Grievance redresses system, suggestion schemes where a woman is empowered to share her views, complaints and suggestions with the Top Management and derive solutions for the same.

Way to achieve a Positive Work Life Balance.

To achieve a positive work Life Balance, women should be proactive and plan her professional and personal schedules well in advance so that both are equally balanced and the end result is satisfaction. If every woman employee follows the given strategies regularly, she would be a successful professional as well as an outstanding family maker.

- Schedule the time effectively at work.
- Explore availability of flexi timing
- Stay focused at work and avoids interruption and distractions at work.
- Schedule activities at family and friends.
- Plan the week end fruitfully.

Impact of demographic variables on work life balance of women employees

Socio economic factors are also found to play a major role in work life balance. Demographic variables such as age, income,

experience, marital status influence the women employees in their work life balance. Various studies were conducted in this direction to determine the impact of demographic variables on work life balance of women employees.

As the age increases there is a juggling in variety of roles that have to play irrespective of having children. Therefore age is one of the constraints of Work Life Balance. Women with dependent children are finding it more difficult to balance their life than those who do not have dependent children. Women who have dependent children would like to spend most of the time with them and their education.

Relationship between stress and Work Life Balance

The number of stress-related disability claims by American employees has doubled according to the Employee Assistance Professionals Association in Arlington, Virginia. Seventy-five to ninety percent of physician visits are related to stress.

Steven L. Sauter, chief of the Applied Psychology and Ergonomics Branch of the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health in Cincinnati, Ohio, states that recent studies show that "the workplace has become the single greatest source of stress". Michael Feuerstein, professor of clinical psychology at the Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences at Bethesda Naval Hospital states, "We're seeing a greater increase in work-related neuro skeletal disorders from a combination of stress and ergonomic stressors".

It is clear that problems caused by stress have become a major concern to both

employers and employees. Symptoms of stress are manifested both physiologically and psychologically. Persistent stress can result in cardiovascular disease problems, a weaker immune system and frequent headaches, stiff muscles, or backache. It can also result in poor coping skills, irritability, jumpiness, insecurity, exhaustion, and difficulty concentrating. Stress may also perpetuate or lead to binge eating and many disorders. The feeling that simply working hard is not enough anymore is acknowledged by many other American workers. "To get ahead, a seventy-hour work week is the new standard. What little time is left is often divided up among relationships, kids, and sleep." This increase in work hours over the past two decades means that less time will be spent with family, friends, and community as well as pursuing activities that one enjoys and taking the time to grow personally and spiritually.

Texas Quick, an expert witness at trials of companies who were accused of overworking their employees, states that "when people get worked beyond their capacity, companies pay the price." Although some employers believe that workers should reduce their own stress by simplifying their lives and making a better effort to care for their health, most experts feel that the chief responsibility for reducing stress should be management.

According to Esther M. Orioli, president of Essi Systems, a stress management consulting firm, "Traditional stress-management programs placed the responsibility of reducing stress on the individual rather than on the organization—where it belongs". No matter how healthy

individual employees are when they start out, if they work in a dysfunctional system, they'll burn out.

Women employees are suffering by three kinds of stress. They are,

- Gender pressure
- Professional pressure
- Societal pressure

Work life balance of women employees in different sector

In IT career women felt pressure of work life balance. Differences also are evident in perception of IT work, mentoring relationships and coping mechanisms relied upon. As more and more women are coming into the work place, child-friendly. Policies are gaining importance in these organisations. New technologies are creating more demand on many working people. Women employees can be reached on a 24/7 basis and this 24/7 access may intrude into their personal time.

Work life balance in IT sector in India suggested that flex time, home working, child care facilities, option to work part time are facilities that need to be introduced and recommended for building a supportive work environment in the organisation. In IT sector work force women says that many women sacrifice their career over family priorities and this is the reason why IT industry has a high proportion of women at lower level.

Patwa (2011) conducted a study to understand work life balance in banking and insurance sector in India. The findings revealed that in spite of certain policies and provisions provided by their organisation for helping them to maintain their work life balance; they still lack in doing so and are not

able to manage their professional life along with their personal life well. It was still observed that the respondents from banking sector enjoyed better work life balance as compared to the respondents from the insurance sector.

Two third of women employees in BPO companies reported that work life imbalance primarily on account of work interference with personal life. The factors that were attributing for work life balance were classified as organisational factor and personal factor.

The organisational factors are

- Work related factor
- Time related factor
- Relationship related factor

The personal factors are

- Lack of family support
- Marital conflict
- Change in sleeping pattern

Women employees in different industries are also facing work life imbalance. Women employees in construction industry not only have a culture of working long hours but also weekend working.

Conclusion

Work-life balance initiatives designed to help employees to balance their work and personal life are not only an option but also a necessity for many employers today. There is a need for organisation to adopt human resource strategies and policies that accommodate the work life need of diverse work force in the current business environment. Working women getting caught

in the work life balance trap will continue to be an ongoing challenge. Careful planning and personal effort is the advice from those who have found balance in both career and home life.

When an individual feels dually satisfied about their personal life and their paid occupation, it mutually benefits the individual, business and society when a person's personal life is balanced with her own job. The work-life balance strategy offers a variety of means to reduce stress levels and increase job satisfaction in the employee while enhancing business benefits for the employer. In our increasingly hectic world, the work-life strategy seeks to find a balance between work and play. A sentence that brings the idea of work life balance to the point is: "Work to live. Don't live to work".

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